

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING SPEAKING SKILL IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In this article, the scientific viewpoints and subjective attitudes of scientists and educators regarding the theoretical and scientific aspects of teaching English science through cutting-edge technologies and interactive methods as well as the factors of interest in this study have been analyzed and expressed. Additionally, we can talk about how information technologies help develop foreign language speaking abilities.*

Keywords: *independent teaching technology, foreign language teaching methods, a global perspective, reflection, communication skills, attitude expression, independent thinking, and creative and novel approaches.*

РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ НАВЫКА ГОВОРЕНИЯ НА ИНОСТРАННОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье проанализированы и выражены научные точки зрения и субъективные взгляды ученых и педагогов на теоретические и научные аспекты преподавания английского языка с помощью передовых технологий и интерактивных методов, а также факторы интереса к данному исследованию. Кроме того, мы можем рассказать о том, как информационные технологии помогают развивать навыки говорения на иностранном языке.*

Ключевые слова: *технология самостоятельного обучения, методика обучения иностранному языку, глобальная перспектива, рефлексия, общение.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English using cutting-edge technologies in the teaching process from early childhood educators to students and students in the educational stages will be one of the main tasks in the upcoming years. The development of human feelings in our country, including the multifaceted cooperation with other countries on the advancement of various spheres, the establishing of relationships in economic, spiritual, and cultural affairs, and particularly the understanding and understanding of one another, appreciation, and respect, are all closely related to the study of English.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Each instructor who teaches English sets the stage for the formation, growth, knowledge acquisition, and development of the student as a person. On the basis of language acquisition, it is crucial for the student to study science, communicate freely, voice their viewpoints, and think independently while being familiar with English language mathematics. Modern methods, interactive methods, support for cutting-edge technologies, and the growth of oral and written communication are therefore thought to have a key influence in the development of their communicative competence.

We are talking about the formation of communicative competence, i.e. ability and readiness to carry out direct communication (speaking, listening comprehension) and indirect

communication (reading, writing foreign texts with understanding). Formation of communicative competence is the main and leading goal of education. Today it is especially popular. The greatest difficulties in communication in a foreign language are experienced by a person when receiving speech by ear. However, oral communication, the role of which is particularly important now, is impossible without understanding the speech of the interlocutor, because in the process of speech interaction, everyone works as both a speaker and a listener.

One of the most controversial aspects of the problem of teaching foreign languages is the methodology of checking and accounting of knowledge, skills and qualifications, their organization and implementation. Control has not yet become a "powerful lever" for improving educational activity and a source that helps to determine the actual state of knowledge and skills in a given subject.

Speaking is an effective speech activity, through which (along with listening) oral communication is carried out. The content of speech is the expression of thought in oral form. Speech is based on pronunciation, lexical, grammatical skills. Speaking is one of the most important areas of teaching in many teaching methods. According to the major or minor role of programming, the statements distinguish initiative (active) speech, reactive (response) speech, reproductive (stochastic) speech. The psychological structure of the speech act includes four stages:

1) stimulating-motivational, in which a person's need for communication is manifested under the influence of a certain motive and the presence of a certain purpose of the statement;

2) analytic-synthetic, presented in the form of folded mental actions for programming and forming thoughts (there is a mechanism for the internal formation of a statement that ensures the selection of words and grammatical forecasting);

3) The executive sound and intonation design of thought (at the initial stage of learning, the transition of the speech program to its implementation occurs through the native language;

4) control, its task is to signal possible errors and contribute to their correction; control implies that the speaker has a norm that is formed as a result of language practice and comparison of his speech with the norm.

The principle of speech orientation. The speech direction of the educational process is not only a practical goal in speech, but the way to this goal is a very practical use of the language. The direction of practical speech is not only a goal, but also unity. The direction of the speech implies the eloquence of exercises, i.e. degree, the criterion of their speech similarity. All of them should be exercises not in pronunciation, but in speech, when the speaker has a clear task and when he makes a speech effect on the interlocutor. The principle of speech orientation also includes the use of communicatively valuable speech material. The use of each expression should be justified by taking into account the intended area of communication (situation) and the communicative value for this category of students. The speech character of the lesson also plays an important role here.

The principle of individualization with the leading role of his personal aspect. Individualization takes into account all characteristics of the student as a person: his abilities, ability to perform speech and educational activities, and mainly his personal characteristics. Individualization is the main realistic means of creating motivation and activity. A person expresses his attitude to the environment in speech. And since this relationship is always individual, therefore speech is individual. In teaching speech in a foreign language, an

individual reaction is possible if the speech task before the student meets his needs and interests as a person. Any statement by the student should be as natural as possible.

Principle of functionality. Any speech unit performs in the process communicate any speech functions. Often students after a course of study knowing words and grammatical forms, they cannot use all of them in speech, because not. transposition occurs (when words and forms are pre-filled with separation speech functions performed by them, words or forms are not related to speech task). Functionality, first of all, determines the selection and organization of material suitable for the communication process. The approach to communication needs is possible only if the means of speech are taken into account and the material is organized around situations and speech tasks rather than around topics of conversation and grammatical events. Unity of lexical, grammatical and phonetic aspects of speech is also necessary.

RESULTS

Social relations are mainly carried out in the country of the language being studied. A person who has learned a language based on them will probably be able to communicate in the specific conditions of the country where the language is being studied. This knowledge is almost unnecessary when communicating with foreigners in our country.

Speech activity is based on the transfer of skills, because the endlessly changing conditions of communication impose new tasks on the speaker every time. If the speaking skills underlying the competence are potentially transferable and therefore the speaking skills are dynamic enough, they can be tackled. Conditional speech situations are a condition for the formation of situational flexibility of speech skills. They create all the conditions for a certain speech unit, in special conditions suitable for the automation of a speech pattern (regularity of use, exemplary), without losing the situation (usually typical of training exercises).

The situation is a prerequisite for the development of skills. Let's say that the need to convince someone of something, naturally, can arise only if the situation is not imposed from the outside, but if it is a consequence or a precursor of the events in which the interlocutors participated. The broader and deeper the connection of a particular situation with all activity, the easier the motive appears: the content of consciousness is human activity.

DISCUSSION

A very good context for the activity can be provided by special films. These event films should be communicative in content (problem), direction (taking into account the field of communication), and have a methodological character. Such a film is shown before each lesson cycle and introduces students to the environment of the next events, based on which the teacher creates situations in the classroom. All educational material, not as a goal, but as a means of teaching speech (texts used for the development of speech, microtexts for mastering words and speech patterns) also rely on film events, but expand and develop them. Except for the exercises in the stage of development of speech skills, the content of many educational exercises could be determined depending on the situation. The inclusion of the activity context is the main condition for the individualization of situations.

CONCLUSIONS

Students and young people are ensured to be well educated and possess a wide range of high qualifications through the use of cutting-edge current technologies, creative approaches, and interactive procedures. It should be noted that for students to study English and acquire information, talents, and skills in the grammatical structure of this language, they must first have

a sufficient understanding of the grammatical structure of their home language and adhere to it rigidly in live speech. The pronoun is one of the lexical components that is particularly active in students' speech. If you have a basic understanding of the pronoun in your original tongue, you can comprehend the same subject in English with ease if you develop those skills.

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